

Derivatization, Separation, Method Development and Validation of Tobramycin and Dexamethasone Eye Drops by Rp- Hplc Method

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ABSTRACT

Tobramycin and Dexamethasone are widely used in combination ophthalmic formulations for the treatment of ocular infections and associated inflammation. Tobramycin is an aminoglycoside antibiotic with potent activity against gram-negative and some gram-positive bacteria, while Dexamethasone is a corticosteroid that suppresses inflammatory responses. This study presents a validated high-performance liquid chromatographic method for the estimation of Tobramycin and Dexamethasone in pharmaceutical ophthalmic solutions using a C₁₈ reversed-phase column. The mobile phase for Dexamethasone consisted of methanol: water (75:25 v/v) at a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min. For Tobramycin, a Tris buffer system was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Due to Tobramycin's weak UV absorbance, samples were derivatized using chemical methods to enhance its detection. Both drugs were effectively separated and derivatized under the optimized chromatographic conditions. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines, demonstrating good linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, and robustness. Results were also compared to the official methods described in the USP, where individual estimations are performed and it is suitable for routine quality control of combined pharmaceutical formulation.

Keywords: Tobramycin, Dexamethasone, Derivatization, Tris buffer, Methanol, RP-HPLC.

INTRODUCTION

Tobramycin is an aminoglycoside antibiotic derived from *Streptomyces tenebrarius* that is used to treat various types of bacterial infections, particularly against Gram-negative organism (Medeiros S, Pinto EC, Cabral LM, Sousa VP et al 2021). Its chemical name is (2S,3R,4S,5S,6R)-4-amino-2-[(1S,2S,3R,4S,6R)-4,6-diamino-3-[(2R,3R,5S,6R)-3-

amino-6-(aminomethyl)-5-hydroxyoxan-2-yl]oxy-2-hydroxycyclohexyl]oxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)oxane-3,5-diol (Mannan A, Asif S, Usmanhane K et al 2017). It exhibits both immediate and delayed illing effects, attributed to different mechanisms. Symptomatic and supportive measures with hemodialysis potentially aiding in the drug (Mittha JN, Kalshetti MS2022).

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Fig:01 Tobramycin

Fig:02 Dexamethasone

Dexamethasone chemical name (8*S*,9*R*,10*S*,11*S*,13*S*,14*S*,16*R*,17*R*)-9-fluoro-11,17-dihydroxy-17-(2-hydroxyacetyl)-10,13,16-trimethyl-7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-dodecahydro-3*H*-cyclopenta[*a*]phenanthren-3-one is a synthetic glucocorticoid used to relieve bacterial ocular infections that require corticosteroid treatment (Maheshwari UD, Patel RM et al 2024). It functions as an adrenergic agent, antiemetic, antineoplastic, immunosuppressive, anti-inflammatory drug, environmental contaminant, and xenobiotic (Pawar AK, Mannepalli C.2023).

Tobramycin and Dexamethasone are frequently co-formulated in ophthalmic preparations for the treatment of ocular infections accompanied by inflammation (Kumar VK.2022). Tobramycin exhibits strong antibacterial activity, while Dexamethasone serves as a potent corticosteroid to suppress inflammation. A suitable simultaneous analytical method has not been reported for the estimation of both drugs, mainly due to their distinct chemical properties and the poor UV absorbance of Tobramycin (Xiong Y, Ping K, Rustum AM et al 2009). In this study, Tobramycin was chemically derivatized to enhance its UV detection, and Dexamethasone was separated and analysed. A accurate, specific, and reproducible method described for the RP-HPLC method for the determination of Tobramycin and Dexamethasone in bulk drug and from pharmaceutical formulation as per ICH guidelines (Pappula N, Palaparathi KK, Govindu A, Suneetha M et al 2020).

EXPERIMENTAL

Tobramycin and Dexamethasone pure samples were procured as a gift sample from Ajanta Pharma Pvt, Hyderabad. Ethanol, Acetonitrile (HPLC grade), Methanol (HPLC grade), and HPLC-grade water were purchased from Merck Mumbai. Tris (Hydroxymethyl)aminomethane, Ether, n-Hexane, 2,4-Dinitrofluorobenzen, and Dimethyl sulfoxide were purchased as HPLC grade reagents from Lobachemical. Pvt. Ltd and SD Fine. Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. Local Commercial eye drops containing 0.3g of tobramycin and 0.1g of dexamethasone were purchased from local market.

LC-INSTRUMENTATION

The liquid chromatography system consists of Shimadzu, Japan (CTO-10AS VP), an intelligent pump (LC-20ATD), coupled with a multiwavelength detector (Shimadzu, Japan) and Rheodyne injector (7725) fitted with a 20 μ l sample loop. Data integration was done by using the lab solution software version for 1 LC peak integration

CHROMATOGRAPHY

Chromatography was performed on RP-C₁₈ column (5 μ m, 4.6 x 250 mm) Hypersil analytical column. The mobile phase for Dexamethasone consisted of methanol: water (75:25 v/v) at a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min. For Tobramycin, Tris buffer system was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min respectively. The mobile phase was filtered through

0.45 µm hydrophilic membrane filter and degassed by sonication prior to use. Detection was done at 228 and 245nm for tobramycin and dexamethasone, respectively, and sensitivity was set at 0.16AUFS.

Preparation Tris buffer

Mobile phase: Dissolve 1 g of tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane in 400 mL of water. Add 10 mL of 1 N sulfuric acid, and dilute with acetonitrile to obtain 1000 mL of solution. Cool, and pass through a filter of 0.2-µm or finer pore size.

PREPARATION OF STANDARD SOLUTION

Tobramycin:

An accurately weighed quantity of 55 mg of Tobramycin was transferred into a 50 mL volumetric flask. About 1 mL of 1 N sulfuric acid was added, followed by sufficient water to dissolve the contents. The solution was sonicated and diluted to volume with water to obtain a final concentration of 0.22 mg/mL. The resulting solution was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane filter before analysis.

Dexamethasone:

Accurately weighed 25 mg of Dexamethasone was transferred to a 25 mL volumetric flask. Approximately 15 mL of diluent (methanol: water, 75:25 v/v) was added to dissolve the compound. The solution was sonicated and made up to volume with the same diluent.

Derivatization of Tobramycin

For derivatization, 4.0 mL of the Tobramycin standard solution was transferred to a 50 mL volumetric flask. To this, 10 mL of (Solution A) and 10 mL of (Solution C) were added.

Solution A: 10 mg/mL of 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene in alcohol.

Solution B: 15 mg/mL of tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane in water.

Solution C: Transfer 40 mL of Solution B to a 200-mL volumetric flask. Add dimethyl sulfoxide while mixing, and dilute with dimethyl sulfoxide to volume

The flask was sealed, shaken, and placed in a constant temperature water bath maintained at 60 ± 2 °C for 50 ± 5 minutes. After heating, the flask was allowed to stand for 10 minutes. Acetonitrile was added to approximately 2 mL below the mark, and after cooling to room temperature, the volume was made up to 50 mL with acetonitrile. This derivatized solution was used for chromatographic analysis.

Analysis of pharmaceutical formulation

Two marketed eye drops, each containing 0.3 mg/mL of tobramycin and 0.1 mg/mL of dexamethasone respectively. Transfer a portion of eye drops containing 4.5 mg of tobramycin to a separator. Add 50 mL of ether, and extract with four 20- to 25-mL portions of water. Combine the water extracts in a 100-mL volumetric flask, and dilute with water to volume. Transfer a portion of eye drops containing 3 mg of dexamethasone to another separator containing 50 mL of n-hexane, and shake. Add 15 mL of Diluent, and shake. Allow the layers to separate, and drain the lower phase into a 50-mL volumetric flask. Repeat the extraction with two 15-mL portions of diluent, combining the lower phase from each extraction in the same 50-mL volumetric flask. Dilute with Diluent to volume, mix, and centrifuge. Use the clear solution for to obtain an concentration of (0.3mg/ml) Tobramycin and (0.1mg/ml) Dexamethasone respectively.

METHOD VALIDATION:

Specificity

The specificity is the ability of the analytical method to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present (Press P 2011). To demonstrate the method, a placebo formulation containing excipients other than the drug was subjected to the sample preparation method as mentioned previously, and the samples thus prepared were then injected into the chromatographic system (Guessan AN, Koffi A, Dally IL, Amin CNC, Gueutin C, Tsapis N, et al 2019).

Selectivity

Selectivity was assessed by analyzing chromatograms of a placebo formulation containing common

excipients present in commercial eye drop formulations (Etabonate L, In T, Dosage C, Using F et al 2015). Placebo samples were prepared to match the expected formulation matrix and tested at equivalent concentrations of 0.3 µg/mL of Tobramycin and 30 µg/mL of Dexamethasone. System responses were evaluated in triplicate for any interference, co-elution, or peak overlap at the retention times of the active drugs (Amjad M, Hussain S et al 2020, Muneera MS 2011).

Linearity

Linearity of the method was established for Tobramycin over the concentration range of 0.1–0.5 µg/mL and Dexamethasone 20–60 µg/mL. Standard solutions were prepared in the mobile phase and injected in triplicate. Calibration curves were constructed by plotting peak areas against the corresponding drug concentrations. The results confirmed excellent linearity for both analytes within the specified ranges (Fanokh M, Owaidi A, Alkhafaji SL et al 2021).

Precision

The system precision was assessed by analyzing standard solutions of Tobramycin (0.4 µg/mL) and Dexamethasone (30 µg/mL) on three consecutive days. For each day, three independent preparations were made for each analyte, and duplicate injections were performed (Renuka Devi. 2013). The consistency of the results was analyzed, confirming the reproducibility of the method under routine laboratory conditions.

Accuracy

Accuracy was evaluated using the standard addition method. Known quantities of Tobramycin (0.24, 0.3, and 0.45 µg) and Dexamethasone (1.6, 20, and 24 µg) were spiked into pre-analyzed formulation samples. The mixtures were extracted, diluted with mobile phase, and analyzed in triplicate using the proposed HPLC method (Sneha et al 2015). Percent recoveries were calculated to assess the method's accuracy across the studied concentration levels (Mannan A, Asif S, Usmanghani K 2017)

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ were determined based on the standard deviation of the response and the slope of the calibration curve, as per the method described by Miller and Miller (2002). LOD was defined as the lowest concentration with a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of approximately 3:1, while LOQ corresponded to an S/N ratio of 10:1 for each analyte (Ankit et al 2013).

Robustness

Robustness of the method was evaluated by introducing deliberate minor variations in chromatographic conditions and assessing their impact on the results (Thamaraikani T, Mounika S, Vijith S. et al 2012). The evaluation was carried out using standard solutions of Tobramycin (0.3 µg/mL) and Dexamethasone (20 µg/mL). The robustness was tested by varying the flow rate (± 0.1 mL/min), percentage of organic phase in the mobile phase ($\pm 2\%$), and pH of the mobile phase (± 0.2 units) from their nominal values. Each variation was tested in duplicate, and the chromatographic responses were monitored for changes in retention time, peak area, and resolution (Rituraj et al. 2013, Sreelaksmi et al. 2020)

Result and Discussion

Optimization of LC procedure

The LC procedure was optimized with a view to develop a method, several trials and derivation techniques has been adopted to increase the sensitivity of the detection for tobramycin and dexamethasone. Tobramycin was derivatized as per standard and it was stable for 6 hrs and subjected to HPLC. Shown in fig: 01 for Tobramycin and shown in fig: 02 for Dexamethasone.

Fig:03 Chromatogram for Tobramycin

Fig:04 Chromatogram for Dexamethasone

Analysis of pharmaceutical formulations

Table:01

COMMERCIAL NAME	DRUG	CONCENTRATION Mg	PEAK AREA	AMOUNT OBTAINED	MEAN	SD	%RSD	%ASSAY
Toba*DM	TOB	0.3	41,297	0.297224886	0.2988	0.0045	1.5209	99.6257
			42,048	0.304017945				
			41,094	0.29538868				
Tobaren D	DEXA	0.1	22594	0.09762123	0.0982	0.00057	0.5799	98.2216
			22706	0.09875457				
			22660	0.09828909				

After separation of Tobramycin and Dexamethasone as per the standard, A single peak at 2.7 min and 6.8 min was observed in the chromatogram of the drug samples tobramycin and dexamethasone and these was no interference from the excipients commonly present in the ophthalmic eye drops. It may be

therefore be inferred that of tobramycin and dexamethasone in the ophthalmic eye drops was detected by this method.

Validation of the Assay method**Specificity**

Placebo formulation for both sample yielded clean chromatogram with no interference from the excipients. The ability of the method to separate the drug with no interference of the excipients indicate the specificity of the method.

Stability of the Analyte in solution

Tobramycin and Dexamethasone was found to be stable in the mobile phase, when the standard solution was analyzed at 6 and 24 h post preparation. No peaks corresponding to the degradation products were observed and there was no significant change in the drug peak area(%RSD<2).

Precision

System precision evaluated by three repeat injections of tobramycin and dexamethasone concentration (0.4 µg/ml and 30 µg/ml) and gave a low RSD value of 0.147% and 0.157%. The quantitative recovery of tobramycin and dexamethasone achieved indicates that there was no interference from excipients present in the formulations table:02 and figure:03,04.

Table:02

DRUG	CONCENTRATION	PEAK AREA	MEAN	SD	%RSD
TOB	0.4	52,029	0.391666667	0.00057735	0.147409
		51,974			
		52,210			
DEX	30	2395048	2397892	3777.967	0.15755965
		2402179			
		2396450			

Fig:05 Chromatogram for Tobramycin

Fig:06 Chromatogram for Dexamethasone

Accuracy

The accuracy was determined by calculating % recoveries of Tobramycin and Dexamethasone. It was

carried out by adding known amount of analyte corresponding to three different concentration levels 80,100 and 120%.

Table:03

NAME	LEVEL	SAMPLE	STANDARD	TOTAL CONCENTRATION µg/mL	PEAK AREA	RECOVERY	% RECOVERY
TOB	80	10	6	16	1269509	16.2722844	98.3266982
	100	10	10	20	1590192	20.2158389	98.9323276
	120	10	14	24	1905085	24.0881917	99.6338799
DEX	80	0.15	0.09	0.24	35245	8.120046	98.52160936
	100	0.15	0.15	0.3	41,062	10.0426	99.57580706
	120	0.15	0.2	0.45	45658	12.17308	98.57817414

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ concentration were found to be respectively 0.01368 µg/ml and 0.04147 µg/ml for Tobramycin and 2.8481 µg/ml and 8.63065 µg/ml for Dexamethasone.

Linearity

The plot of drug peak area versus the concentration was linear over the concentration range of 0.1-0.5 µg/ml and 20-60 µg/ml for Tobramycin and

Dexamethasone. The value of r^2 and 0.9934 and 0.997 which are well within acceptance limit ($r^2 < 1$).

Fig:07

Linearity for Tobramycin

Fig:08: Chromatogram for Tobramycin

Fig: 09 Linearity for Dexamethasone

Fig:10 Chromatogram for Dexamethasone

Robustness

The method's robustness was assessed by introducing minor variations in chromatographic conditions using standard solutions of Tobramycin (0.4 mg/mL) and Dexamethasone (30 mg/mL). Flow rate

(± 0.1 mL/min), organic phase composition ($\pm 2\%$), and mobile phase pH (± 0.2 units) were altered. Each change was tested in duplicate, and effects on retention time, peak area, and resolution were evaluated.

Table:04 Temperature changes for Tobramycin

PARAMETERS	PEAK AREA	MEAN	SD	% RSD
Minus temperature (28C)	517636	514220	8712.42	1.694
	520708			
	504318			
Plus temperature(32C)	53,071	52,903	185.53	0.355

Table:05 Flow rate changes for Tobramycin

PARAMETERS	PEAK AREA	MEAN	SD	% RSD
Plus flow rate (1.1 ml min-1)	53,007	52,907	101.52	0.191
	52,804			
	52,909			
Minus flow rate (0.9ml min-1)	51,869	51,873	181.53	0.349
	52,057			
	51,694			

Table:06 Temperature changes for Dexamethasone

PARAMETERS	PEAK AREA	MEAN	SD	% RSD
Minus temperature (38C)	2186052	2194737.67	7970.349072	0.363157255
	2201716			
	2196445			
Plus temperature(42C)	2404154	2391451.33	25514.40272	1.066900353

Table:07 Flow rate changes for Dexamethasone

PARAMETERS	PEAK AREA	MEAN	SD	% RSD
Plus flow rate (1.3 ml min-1)	2425042	2411226.333	17039.00749	0.706653177
	2392187			
	2416450			
Minus flow rate (1.1 ml min-1)	2295248	2297961	3697.858434	0.160919112
	2302173			
	2296462			

CONCLUSION

The RP-HPLC assay method development for Tobramycin and Dexamethasone is precise, specific, and rapid. The statistical analysis proves that the method is reproducible and selective for the analysis of Tobramycin and Dexamethasone as ophthalmic eye drops. The run time less than 10 min was found to be practicably advantageous for the use of this method in routine analysis. It may be extended to study the degradation kinetics of Tobramycin and Dexamethasone and also for its estimation in plasma and other biological fluids.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

No conflict of interest

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